

Effect of Self Learning Module on Socio-Academic Development of Kindergarten Pupils

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Abstract. This study sought to determine the effect of a self-learning module on the socio-emotional development of kindergarten pupils. It also aimed to determine the factors of independent learning affecting the emotional development of kindergarten pupils. This study was conducted at Sta. Cruz Central Elementary School, Sta. Cruz South District, Division of Davao del Sur. The subjects of this study were 41 kindergarten pupils: 20 were from section A, which was the control group, and 21 were from section B, which was the experimental group. The composition of these two sections was homogeneous, with learners from both sections A and B having identical grades. This study made use of the non-random assignment of subjects, involving all learners from both sections A and B as subjects of the study. This study utilized the new normal learning modality, a blended learning approach where teachers provided modules and met learners online, adhering to the protocols of the Inter-Agency Task Force (IATF). The researcher met the learners online for follow-up sessions on what had been printed in the module. This study revealed that the utilization of the self-learning module increased the socio-emotional development of kindergarten pupils. It also revealed a significant difference between the post-test scores of the control and experimental groups.

KEY WORDS

1. Socio-Academic Development
2. Self Learning Modules
3. Blended Learning

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1. Introduction

Self learning is an individualized mode of education. Nowadays, face to face learning is not implemented to the mode of learning and the distance learning became popular. A kindergarten pupil has a characteristic that needs the assistance of teachers. The effect of self learning will arise on the socio emotional development of kindergarten pupils. Technology is undeniably changing the face of education, and the technology impact is widely felt by educators and learners. The Department of Education (DepEd) in the Philippines offered two alternative distance learning modalities, namely, pure online and hybrid (online and offline), which were supplemented with contextualized and standardized self-learning modules (SLM) crafted by teachers for each region of the country. In addition, the DepEd generated the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELC) as a way of decongesting the curriculum and making schooling during the pandemic less stressful (DepEd, 2020). The MELC-aligned SLM is the backbone of distance learning aimed at making education accessible to students, both online

and offline, most especially to those who live in far-flung rural areas without internet access (DepEd, 2020). Constructivist learning theory positions students as active agents in the construction of knowledge from meaningful interpretations of real-life experiences (Bada Olusegun, 2019).

Problem-based learning has a significant and positive effect on students' academic performance, achieving higher marks on all assessments than the control group who experienced traditional approach, according to a meta-analysis of studies, mostly from Asia, conducted from 2016 to 2020 (Funa Prudente, 2020). Prior studies have shown that parents satisfied with the learning and involvement opportunities provided by schools have lower parenting stress and higher parental involvement (Lau Ng, 2019). In contrast, when parents perceive that the school is not supportive and is not responsive to children's need in their teaching and collaboration with parents, parents experience a loss in the need or desire for cooperation that manifests in dissatisfaction (Griffith, 2020). The finding provides further evidence that having younger children at home may be stress inducing and that online learning may be regarded as challenging for younger children's families. In Indonesia, a study was conducted to examine the impact of classroom design on

socio-emotional development. The study revealed that classrooms featuring flexible seating arrangements and sufficient space for movement were conducive to the cultivation of autonomy, collaboration, and engagement among students. The surrounding environment played a role in fostering constructive interpersonal connections and promoting improved emotional welfare (Suryani, 2019). In the Philippines, a study was conducted to examine the impact of peer relationships and classroom environment. The study revealed that a favorable and inclusive classroom climate fostered prosocial behavior, empathy, and cooperation among students. The conducive environment fostered the formation of robust peer connections, thereby enhancing the socio-emotional development of students. Furthermore, the integration of cooperative learning strategies in educational settings has been found to cultivate favorable peer interactions, enhance students' communication proficiencies, and augment their emotional intelligence (Fitriana, 2019). In the Division of Davao Del Sur, specifically in Sta Cruz Central Elementary School, a pupil experiencing an independent learning affects their socio emotional development. The researcher being a teacher in the above educational institution would like to explore other dimensions in solving the merging problem. Hence, this is action research.

2. Methodology

This chapter discusses the researcher method, the researched design, the placed and time, the researched instruments, test construction and validation, scaling, data gathering procedure and the data analysis.

2.1. Research Design—This studied made used of the quasi experimental researched design which was a non-equivalent controlled group pretest-posttest design. Non-equivalent design was a good design when the researcher had access to one group for experimentation (vockel 1983). The researcher opted to used

this design because the subjects of the studied were intact group of learners.

2.2. Research Respondents—This studied had been conducted in sta. Cruz central elementary school, sta. Cruz south district, division of davao del sur. The subjects of this studied had been the 41 kindergarten pupils – 20 were from

section a which had been the controlled group and 21 were from section b which had been the experimental group. The composition of these two sections was homogeneous. Both learners from sections a and b had identical grades. This study made use of the non-random assignment of subjects where all learners of both sections a and b were involved as subjects of the study.

2.3. Research Instrument—This study will utilize the new normal learning modality. It is a blended learning where teacher gave module at the same meet the learners online but adhering to the protocols of Inter-agency Task Force (IATF). The researcher has to meet the learn-

2.4. Data Gathering Procedure—At the outset of data gathering procedure, the researcher will draft a letter seeking for permission that this research study be conducted were sent to the Schools Division Superintendent of Davao Sur, Dr. Nelson Lopez, CESO V and the school principal of Sta. Cruz Central Elementary School. While letters seeking for permission were delivered to the Schools Division Superintendent and the school principal concerned, the researcher constructed a questionnaire and have it validated by the experts preferably the experts of the study. After per-

2.5. Data Analysis—The following statistical tools will be used in the analysis and interpretation the responses in this study. Mean will be use to describe the socio-academic skills

ers on line for a follow up session of what has been printed in the module. The pre and post-performance test consist of 2 activities in the self-Learning Module that was eventually determined the socio-academic skills of the research subjects. The pretest will be administered to all subjects prior to the treatment. The pretest will be very helpful to assess the socio-academic skills of the kindergarten learners. On the hand, post test will be administered to measure the effect of the treatment. To determine the socio-academic skills of the kindergarten learners, the following continuum will be use based on DepEd rating system.

mission has been granted that this study be conducted in Sta. Cruz Central Elementary School and after the research questionnaire has been thoroughly examined by the expert validators, the researcher will administer pretest to both controlled and experimental class and eventually commences her experiment. After three weeks of experimentation, the researcher will administer posttest to both sections. Scores of the subjects will be submitted to the statistician for statistical computation after which the researcher will make analysis and interpretation on the data gathered.

of the kindergarten learners in both pretest and posttest scores. Eta square will be used to measure the magnitude of effect of self-learning module on the socio-academic skills development of the kindergarten learners.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the discussion of the problems in this study. They are discussed thoroughly, analyzed and interpreted under the following headings and sequence: Pre-test Scores of the Learners, Post-test Scores of the Learners and the Significant Relationship of the pre-tests and Post-tests Scores.

Interval	Scale	Level	Criteria
96 and above	5	Advanced	The student at this level exceeds the core requirements in terms of knowledge, skills and understandings and can transfer them automatically and flexibly through authentic performance tasks.
89 - 95	4	Proficient	The student at this level has developed the fundamental knowledge and skills and core understandings and can transfer them independently through authentic performance tasks.
82 - 88	3	Approaching Proficiency	The student at this level has developed the fundamental knowledge and skills and core understandings and, with little guidance from the teacher and/or with some assistance from peers, can transfer these understandings through authentic performance tasks.
75 - 81	2	Developing	The student at this level possesses the minimum knowledge and skills and core understandings, but needs help throughout the performance of authentic tasks.
Below 75	1	Beginning	The student at this level struggles with understanding; prerequisite and fundamental knowledge and/or skills have not been acquired or developed adequately to aid understanding.

Pre-Test Score of Learners Table 1 disclosed Beginning while the experimental group got the pre-test scores of the kindergarten pupils. mean of 18.34 or Beginning. The controlled group got the mean of 17.46 or

Table 1. Pre-Test Score of Pupils

Group	n	Mean	Rating	Descriptive Equivalent
Controlled Group Pre-test	20	14.46	57.44	Beginning
Experimental Group Pre-test	21	15.34	61.36	Beginning

It can be gleaned from the table that during pre-test the experimental group has a higher mean rating over the controlled group although both belongs Beginning level. This finding is congruent to the idea of Mohamed Toran (2019) who said that the child’s capacity to regulate their emotions and navigate social interactions will significantly impact their achievements within educational settings, home, environments, and everyday circumstances. Self-learning modules offer learners the opportunity to exercise autonomy and exert control over their learning process, thereby fostering the development of self-regulation skills such as goal-setting, time management, and self-reflection. The presence of autonomy in one’s life facilitates the development of a sense of self-efficacy, which plays a vital role in the advancement of socio-emotional growth (Hartnett, 2019).

Table 2. Post-Test Score of Pupils

Group	n	Mean	Rating	Descriptive Equivalent
Controlled Group Post-test	20	20.13	80.52	Developing
Experimental Group Post-test	21	21.97	87.88	Approaching Proficiency

Shown in table 2 are the post-test scores of the kindergarten pupils. The controlled group got the mean of 20.13 or Developing while the experimental group gained the mean of 21.97 or Approaching Proficiency. It can be gleaned from the table that during post-test the experimental group has a higher mean rating over the controlled group. It got a mean rating increase of 6.63 from a mean rating of 15.34 to 21.97. This means that experimental group has a far better performance than the controlled group. This finding is congruent to the idea of Khalid (2019) who cited that self-learning modules have the capacity to cater to the unique learning styles and paces of individuals, thereby accommodating a wide range of learners with diverse needs. The promotion of inclusivity within educational settings has the potential to cultivate a conducive learning environment that facilitates the development of social-emotional competencies, including but not limited to acceptance, respect, and appreciation of diversity. Engaging in self-directed learning activities facilitates the cultivation of critical thinking and problem-solving abilities in kindergarten-aged children. Independent exploration fosters the development of critical thinking skills in children, as they are prompted to engage in the processes of analysis, evaluation, and synthesis of information. This process facilitates the development of individuals’ capacity for critical thinking, establishing connections, and devising solutions to the various challenges they may face (Kotrikadze, 2020).

Table 3. Test on the Significant Difference between the Pre-Test and Post-Test Score

Test	df	t-value	p-value	Test Remarks
Pre-test and Post-test	23	-5.28	.0233	Significant

Table 3 shows the test on the significant difference between the pretest and post-test score of the respondents. It registered a t-value of -5.28 with a p-value of .0233 which is lesser than .05 level of significance which means that there is a significant difference between the pretest scores and the post test scores of the kindergarten pupils. This implies that the used of self-learning module in teaching kindergarten pupils have contributed the effectiveness in socio-academic development which is revealed by the scores of the kindergarten pupils. This finding is in line with the statement of Davis (2019) who said that Self-learning modules frequently integrate interactive components, such as games, simulations, and multime-

dia resources, in order to augment engagement and motivation. The incorporation of interactive elements within educational materials enhances the learning process for young children, resulting in a more engaging and impactful educational experience. It functions as supplementary resources to enhance classroom instruction or as tools for reinforcing and expanding learning beyond the confines of the traditional classroom environment. The inclusion of these modules offers supplementary avenues for children to engage in practice and application of acquired knowledge, thereby facilitating the development of a more profound comprehension and proficiency in various concepts (Turner, 2021).

Table 4. Test on the Magnitude of Difference between the Pretest and Posttest Scores of the Kindergarten Pupils

N	t-value	Eta2	Descriptive Value	Decision
41	-4.42	0.422	Large Effect	Relatively Adapt

Table 4 highlights the test of self-learning module on the socio-academic development of kindergarten pupils. It generated an Eta2 value of 0.422 which signifies large effect. This implies that teachers should look for a strategy in designing effective self-learning module for kindergarten pupils. Effective self-learning modules play a pivotal role in nurturing holistic development among kindergarten pupils, fostering independence, cultivating critical skills, adapting to individual needs, promoting lifelong learning habits, and building social connections. Self-learning modules facilitate the development of critical thinking and problem-solving abilities. Through the provision of chal-

lenging tasks and open-ended inquiries, children are stimulated to engage in critical thinking, analyze information, and generate innovative solutions. This not only enhances individuals' cognitive abilities but also fosters the development of their problem-solving and decision-making skills, which are crucial for continuous learning throughout their lives. Similarly, engaging in self-directed learning activities facilitates the cultivation of critical thinking and problem-solving abilities in kindergarten-aged children. Independent exploration fosters the development of critical thinking skills in children, as they are prompted to engage in the processes of analysis, evaluation, and synthesis

of information. This process facilitates the development of individuals' capacity for critical thinking, establishing connections, and devising solutions to the various challenges they may face (Kotrikadze, 2020).

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This chapter displays the summary of the findings, conclusions and recommendations drawn out by the researcher after the analysis and interpretation of the findings had been made.

4.1. Findings—This study sought to determine the effect of self-learning modules on the socio-academic development of kindergarten pupils. This study made use of quasi-experimental research design, which is a non-equivalent control group pretest-posttest design. Non-equivalent design is a good design when the researcher has access to one group for experimentation (Vockel 1983). The researcher opted to use this design because the subjects of the study are intact group of learners. This study was conducted in Sta. Cruz Central Elementary School, Sta. Cruz South District. The subjects of this study were the 41 kindergarten pupils – 20 are from section A which comprised the controlled group and 21 are from section B composed the experimental group. The composition of these two sections is heterogeneous therefore pupils of sections A and B have identical range of performance. This study made use of the non-random assignment of subjects where all learners of both sections A and B were involved as subjects of the study. This study revealed that the utilization of self-learning module has increased the socio-academic development of kindergarten pupils. It also revealed that there is magnitude of difference between the post test scores of the controlled and experimental groups.

4.2. Conclusions—Based on the collective findings on this study, the following conclusions are drawn: The pre-test scores of the grade five pupils both the controlled and experimental

groups is at the Beginning level. The post-test scores of the controlled group is at the Developing level while the post test scores of the experimental group is at the Approaching Proficiency level.

4.3. Recommendations—In the light of the findings drawn out by the researcher in this study, the following recommendations are offered: It is recommended that teachers teaching kindergarten should used self-learning module as a strategy that would further develop their socio-academic skills. By creating a supportive learning environment, fostering self-regulated learning, promoting collaboration and communication skills, cultivating critical thinking abilities, and supporting students' socio-emotional well-being, teachers lay the foundation for academic success, personal growth, and lifelong learning. The school heads should promote the use of self-learning module as a strategy that offer students autonomy, flexibility, and personalized learning experiences. Within this context, the significance of socio-academic development becomes even more pronounced. A school policy about the utilization of self-learning module can be issued. Besides, he can invite the teacher-researcher to demoteach during LAC session using play as a strategy in teaching. For future researchers, it is strongly recommended that a relative study on the use of role play as a strategy in teaching will be conducted. Another dimension in teaching can serve as another indicator.

5. References

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